

Failure Analysis for Electronic Packaging Materials: A Comparative Study of Pulsed Thermography and Lock-in Thermography

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Abstract—Electronic packaging plays a critical role in ensuring the reliability and performance of electronic systems. As various materials are used in these systems, each with distinct properties, failure analysis of each is key to improving overall system reliability. This paper presents a comparative study of two non-destructive testing (NDT) methods—pulsed thermography (PT) and lock-in thermography (LIT) — for failure analysis in electronic packaging materials. The study focuses on defect detection in copper (Cu), aluminum (Al), and polymer, which are widely used in electronic packaging due to their distinct thermal characteristics. Experimental results are evaluated using signal-to-background contrast (SBC). To enhance thermal contrast, three post-processing techniques—pulse phase thermography (PPT), principal component thermography (PCT), and thermographic signal reconstruction (TSR)—were applied to the PT results. These results were then compared with the optimal performance of LIT. The findings demonstrate that both methods have distinct advantages and limitations: PT offers faster detection, while LIT provides higher sensitivity for materials with higher thermal diffusivity. This study enhances the understanding of how these techniques can be effectively applied in electronic packaging failure analysis.

Index Terms—Failure Analysis, Non-destructive Testing, Pulsed Thermography, Lock-in Thermography, Electronic Packaging Material

I. INTRODUCTION

Electronic packaging is defined as the process of establishing electrical and mechanical connections within the electronic packaging system. The diverse properties of electronic packaging materials significantly influence package reliability and performance. Non-destructive testing (NDT) methods, particularly pulsed thermography (PT) and lock-in thermography (LIT), are crucial for failure analysis and quality assessment of electronic packages, enabling the effective identification of defects such as voids, delamination, and cracks.

PT and LIT are infrared-based techniques that rely on the principle of thermal wave propagation. Both methods induce temperature variations on the surface of the sample,

but they differ in their excitation approaches. PT [1] involves the application of a brief heat pulse to capture the transient thermal response. In contrast, LIT [1], [2] employs continuous, modulated heating to analyze the amplitude of the thermal wave and the phase shift between the excitation and response. In the context of electronic packaging, the thermal behavior of materials varies due to differences in thermal properties, including conductivity, heat capacity, density, and thermal diffusivity. These disparities influence the propagation and response of heat within materials. Consequently, detecting defects in diverse materials poses a substantial challenge.

Fig. 1: Schematic of the experimental setup for PT (a) and LIT (b). A flash lamp is used as the excitation source for the PT setup, and a laser is used for LIT. The IR camera captures thermal images pattern.

This paper aims to compare the effectiveness of pulsed and lock-in thermography for detecting defects in electronic packaging materials, with a specific focus on Cu, Al, and polymer. Cu and Al are widely used for their excellent thermal conductivity, while polymer is commonly employed as an insulating material. The study evaluates the advantages and limitations of each method, offering insights into their applicability for failure analysis in the field of electronic packaging.

The paper is structured as follows: Section II introduces a literature review of PT and LIT. Section III outlines the

methodology, including sample selection, defect size, experiment setup, and evaluation metric. Section IV presents the results and discussion, comparing the performance of both methods in detecting defects across materials. Finally, Section V concludes the paper with a summary of findings and outlook for future research.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Pulsed Thermography

In PT, illustrated in Fig.1a, a strong but short heat pulse is applied to the sample using a high-power excitation source, such as a flash lamp, and the resulting surface temperature is captured by an infrared (IR) camera. For a semi-infinite sample, the thermal response is described by the one-dimensional solution of the Fourier Equation for a Dirac delta function [3]:

$$T(z, t) = T_0 + \frac{Q}{e\sqrt{\pi t}} \exp\left(-\frac{z^2}{4\alpha t}\right), \quad (1)$$

where T_0 is the initial temperature [K], Q is the absorbed energy [J/m^2], $e = \sqrt{k\rho C_p}$ is thermal effusivity [$\text{W}\sqrt{\text{s}}/\text{m}^2\text{K}$] and $\alpha = k/\rho C_p$ is the thermal diffusivity [m^2/s], with k the thermal conductivity [$\text{W}/(\text{m}\cdot\text{K})$], ρ the mass density [kg/m^3], C_p the specific heat [$\text{J}/\text{kg}\cdot\text{K}$].

After the pulsed heating, the temperature of the material changes rapidly because of the thermal propagation by diffusion under the surface. The presence of a defect modifies this diffusion rate, so when observing the surface temperature above the defect, temperature values differ compared to those above the sound areas. The temperature difference ΔT at the surface $z = 0$ follows to [3]:

$$\Delta T(z = 0, t) = \frac{Q}{e\sqrt{\pi t}}. \quad (2)$$

B. Lock-in Thermography

In LIT, the sample is periodically heated at a specific modulation frequency, known as the lock-in frequency f [Hz], while an IR camera records the material's thermal response [4]. The principle is shown in Fig.1b.

The periodic transfer of heat generates a time-dependent thermal wave, which in one dimension is given by [2], [5]:

$$\begin{aligned} T(z, t) &= T_0 \exp\left(-\frac{z}{\mu}\right) \exp\left(i\left(\omega t - \frac{z}{\mu}\right)\right) \\ &= A(z) \exp(i(\omega t - \phi(z))), \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where thermal diffusion length μ [mm] is determined by the lock-in frequency $f = \omega/2\pi$ [2]:

$$\mu = \sqrt{\frac{\alpha}{\pi f}}. \quad (4)$$

The diffusion length μ increases with higher thermal diffusivity α and decreases with increasing modulation frequency f . The term $A(z)$ represents the amplitude with depth, $\phi(z)$ denotes the depth-dependent phase shift [6].

C. Comparative Studies

Previous research has established the foundational applications of PT and LIT in various fields, including aerospace [7], batteries [8], and microelectronics [9], [10], etc.

For PT, Chung et al. [11] summarized the latest data processing techniques to enhance defect detectability. D'Accardi et al. [12] demonstrated that, when applied to Al, principal component thermography (PCT) maximizes the signal-to-background contrast (SBC), whereas pulse phase thermography (PPT) enables accurate defect size estimation with minimal error. Similarly, Pareek et al. [13] reported that combining thermographic signal reconstruction (TSR) with PCT yields optimal PT performance in polymer, proving PT's effectiveness for defect detection in polymeric materials. For LIT, Meola et al. [6] applied LIT to aerospace structures composed of various materials (composites, hybrid composites, sandwiches, metals) with diverse damage types (delamination, impact damage, fatigue failure), demonstrating its effectiveness in defect detection capabilities. Ranjit et al. [14] investigated LIT for evaluating defect size and depth.

Chatterjee et al. [15] compared PT, LIT, and frequency modulated thermal wave imaging (FMTWI) for detecting defects in carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) samples. Their findings indicated that PT provides the highest SNR for shallow defects in CFRP, while PT, LIT, and FMTWI perform similarly for deeper defects. FMTWI addresses the "blind frequency" limitation of LIT using frequency-modulated excitation. Ibarra-Castanedo et al. [16] compared PT, LIT, and vibrothermography (VT) for aerospace components. Their results showed that the optimal method depends on the application: PT excels in speed, LIT offers precise depth control using modulation excitation, and VT is particularly effective for localized defects. Similarly, Ben-Larbi et al. [17] examined PT and LIT performance in aerospace materials.

In the field of electronic packaging, some research have applied thermography techniques to detect defects in electronic packaging, such as Wargulski et al. [9] proposed using temporary foil lamination instead of spray coating to improve the detectability of low emissivity materials in PT. Panahandeh et al. [10] proved that PT can be employed for inline inspection during production. However, these studies focused on PT and did not provide a comparison with LIT.

Overall, prior studies have mainly focused on comparing different techniques within the same material or comparing different materials using a single technique. A comprehensive comparison study of PT and LIT across materials remains unexplored. This study simplifies such complexity by focusing on fundamental material properties in electronic packaging, enabling a comparison of PT and LIT's performance.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Sample Materials and Defect

The quality of the die attach is important for the reliability of stacked structures, as it ensures connections between the die and the substrate (Fig. 1). Defects such as voids, delamination,

and cracks in the die attach layer can lead to thermal failures, thereby affecting the performance of the electronic packaging system. In defect detection research, introducing controlled defects in the die attach is challenging because precise control over their size, location, and type requires specialized equipment and techniques, which significantly increase fabrication complexity and cost. In this reduced complexity study, Cu is employed as a high diffusivity stand-in for Si, which is commonly used as a chip material. The thermal diffusivity difference between Cu and Si is less than 30 % (Table I), allowing the excitation frequency window and defect-depth scaling derived from Cu to be translated to Si, while offering simpler machining and lower costs. Additionally, polymers are included in this study because of their widespread use as electronic molding compounds (EMCs) in electronic packaging.

Since the thermal properties of Cu and polymer differ significantly, with Cu having the higher thermal diffusivity and polymer the lower, Al was also selected as an intermediate material to bridge this gap ($\alpha_{Cu} > \alpha_{Al} > \alpha_{Polymer}$). This approach enables an investigation into how varying thermal properties (high, intermediate, and low diffusivity) affect thermal wave propagation and defect detection.

For this study, Cu (EN-CW008A), Al (EN-AW5754), and polymer (resin-bonded cellulose laminate) were selected, as detailed in Table I.

TABLE I: Material properties

Property	Si	Cu	Al	Polymer
k [W/(m·K)]	148	397	160	0.3
ρ [kg/m ³]	2329	8940	2660	1350
C_p [J/(kg·K)]	700	385	921	1250
α [m ² /s]	$0.9e-4$	$1.15e-4$	$6.53e-5$	$1.78e-7$

Each sample is a cube with a side length of 20 mm, the sample thickness is 6 mm for Cu and Al, and 4 mm for polymer. Furthermore, to compensate for the low emissivity of Cu and Al, the top surfaces were sprayed with a thin layer of high IR emissivity black paint, shown in Fig.2.

Fig. 2: The top surfaces of Cu and Al samples are coated with black paint. Each sample is a cube measuring 20 mm per side. The depths D are 6 mm for Cu and Al, and 4 mm for the polymer. Defect depths Z are 0.3 mm and 0.5 mm, with a diameter of 3 mm.

B. Experiment setup

For PT, three key parameters must be considered in the experimental setup: camera frame rate, excitation power, and acquisition time. The TIFAS@IR lab (Fig. 3a) from Berliner Nanotest und Design GmbH is used for PT experiment, which includes a flash lamp with an energy of approximately 1.0 kJ, an IR camera Optris Xi 400 with a resolution of 382×288 IR pixels and with a noise equivalent temperature difference (NETD) of less than 80 mK. The frame rate of the camera is 80 Hz. The acquisition time was 2.5 seconds for each sample. Fig.4a shows the raw data from PT, which are analyzed using three post-processing methods (PCT [18], PPT [19], and TSR [20]) to obtain the maximum SBC value.

Fig. 3: Experiment setup of PT (a) and LIT (b). Flash lamp and laser are thermal excitation of PT and LIT, respectively. The sample holder is a support plate with needles to increase the thermal resistance between the sample and the measurement base.

For LIT, the camera is InfraTec ImageIR 8300®, which has a resolution of 640×512 IR pixels and NETD of less than 20 mK (Fig. 3b). The laser used in this study, produced by nLight company, offers a maximum output power of 45 W and a typical peak wavelength of 878.6 nm. The frequency f and thermal diffusivity α are key parameter, which influences the diffusion length μ . To evaluate performance across different materials, varying modulation frequencies were employed. For Cu and Al with higher thermal diffusivity, 0.5 Hz, 1 Hz, 5 Hz, and 10 Hz are selected. In contrast, for the polymer, 0.1 Hz, 0.5 Hz, 1 Hz and 5 Hz are used due to its lower thermal diffusivity (Equation 4). The experiments for Cu and Al include 900 lock-in periods, while the polymer experiments include 90 lock-in periods since they have different thermal diffusivities and modulation frequencies. For the IR camera, there are four frames per lock-in period. Fig.4b shows the raw data from LIT, which are analyzed using the fast Fourier transform (FFT) [21] to extract the amplitude and phase.

C. Evaluation metric

SBC is a widely used metric for evaluating the effectiveness of thermograph inspection results obtained from PT and LIT [12], [13]. It quantifies the thermal contrast between the defective and sound (defect-free) regions. The defect area and sound area are shown in Fig.5, where the defect area is marked in red and the sound area in blue.

Fig. 4: Temperature-time raw data of the polymer with a 0.3 mm defect from PT (a) and LIT at 0.1 Hz (b).

Fig. 5: Phase image of Al (0.3 mm) at 5 Hz from LIT (a) with high-lighted areas: red indicates defect region, blue indicates sound region (b).

SBC is expressed as:

$$SBC = \frac{abs(\mu_D - \mu_S)}{\sigma_S}, \quad (5)$$

where μ_D is the mean pixel value of the defect area, μ_S is the mean pixel value of the selected sound areas, and σ_S is the standard deviation of the selected sound areas.

A defect can be detected when the SBC satisfies the following condition [12], [13]:

$$abs(\mu_D - \mu_S) > c * \sigma_S, \quad (6)$$

$$SBC = \frac{abs(\mu_D - \mu_S)}{\sigma_S} > c = 2,$$

where c is a detection threshold coefficient. When the threshold c is larger than two, it typically indicates a defect. Under the assumption of normally distributed background noise, values more than $\pm 2\sigma_s$ from the mean occur with a combined probability of less than 5%. Therefore, a contrast ratio greater than 2 between defect and sound regions—when normalized by the standard deviation of the sound region—is often used as a practical threshold for identifying defects [12], [22].

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Pulsed thermography results

PCT, PPT, and TSR were applied to PT to enhance thermal contrast. PCT identifies dominant thermal patterns in image

sequences based on singular value decomposition (SVD) [18]. In PPT, the Fourier transform converts thermal responses from the time domain to the frequency domain for phase and amplitude analysis [19]. TSR employs polynomial curve fitting to reconstruct the thermal decay curve and extract defect-related features [20]. The SBC values from these methods are summarized in Table II.

TABLE II: SBC value from different methods of PT

Material	Defect (mm)	PCT	PPT		TSR	
			Amp	Phase	1st	2nd
Cu	0.3	2.53	1.20	1.19	0.70	0.72
	0.5	2.03	1.03	0.98	0.49	0.55
Al	0.3	10.41	5.23	3.81	3.58	4.21
	0.5	5.14	4.97	3.02	3.42	3.51
Polymer	0.3	15.44	9.34	26.35	49.79	22.92
	0.5	9.41	6.97	8.18	32.87	16.08

For the material with the highest thermal diffusivity, Cu, the maximum SBC values obtained using PCT of 0.3 mm defect is 2.53 and of 0.5 mm defect is 2.03. According to the defect detection criterion defined in Equation 6, these SBC values are over the threshold of two, indicating that defects in Cu can be reliably detected. For the material with the lowest thermal diffusivity, polymer, the maximum SBC values using the first deviation of TSR are 49.79 at 0.3 mm defect and 32.87 at 0.5 mm defect. For Al, whose thermal diffusivity lies between Cu and polymer, the maximum SBC values using PCT are 10.41 at 0.3 mm defect and 5.14 at 0.5 mm defect.

B. Lock-in thermography results

The LIT results were analyzed to extract amplitude and phase, as summarized in Table III. The detection frequency varies significantly with material type and defect size. For Cu, the 0.3 mm defect achieves the highest amplitude SBC (3.44) and phase SBC (3.18) at a low frequency of 0.5 Hz. For the 0.5 mm defect, the optimal amplitude SBC (3.55) occurs at 1 Hz, while the optimal phase SBC (2.54) remains at 0.5 Hz. For polymer, the phase SBC reaches exceptionally high values (31.20 and 22.33) at 0.1 Hz, with amplitude SBC peaks (10.18 and 6.67) also appearing in 0.1 Hz. However, when the frequency increases to 5 Hz, SBC values drop sharply. Al, with thermal diffusivity between that of Cu and polymer, shows the following trends: for the 0.3 mm defect, the amplitude peak (5.54) occurs at 1 Hz, whereas the phase peak (7.63) appears at 10 Hz; for the 0.5 mm defect, the best amplitude (2.26) is at 0.5 Hz, and the best phase (5.30) is at 10 Hz.

As shown in Fig. 6, numerous spots are observed in the thermal images of Cu. Although Al does not exhibit such spots, its amplitude images still reveal non-uniformity, which can be attributed to uneven thickness of the spray coating. This presents a challenge when using spray coatings on materials with low emissivity and should be addressed in future work.

Fig. 6: PT and LIT images corresponding to the maximum SBC values in Tables IV.

TABLE III: SBC Values of Amplitude and Phase from LIT

Material	Frequency (Hz)	Z = 0.3 mm		Z = 0.5 mm	
		Amplitude	Phase	Amplitude	Phase
Cu	0.5	3.44	3.18	2.85	2.54
	1	2.36	1.74	3.55	2.00
	5	2.03	0.95	2.78	1.03
	10	1.89	1.62	2.22	1.07
Al	0.5	5.04	2.81	2.26	2.11
	1	5.54	1.45	2.01	0.81
	5	4.79	6.76	1.67	5.21
	10	2.50	7.63	1.62	5.30
Polymer	0.1	10.18	31.20	5.69	22.33
	0.5	9.39	22.79	0.70	17.55
	1	0.85	11.16	0.15	2.04
	5	0.14	2.65	0.08	2.52

C. Discussion

The maximum SBC of PT and LIT are compare in Table IV. The results show a correlation between defect depth and the thermal properties of Cu, Al, and polymer in both PT and LIT. In both PT and LIT, the SBC values generally decrease as defect depth increases from 0.3 mm to 0.5 mm across all three materials, confirming that shallower defects are easier to detect regardless of whether the material has high or low thermal diffusivity. The only exception occurs in LIT measurements of Cu, where the amplitude SBC at 0.5 mm (3.55) is marginally higher than at 0.3 mm (3.44), though this difference is negligible.

Besides the defect size, thermal diffusivity also influences detection performance. For high diffusivity Cu, LIT consis-

TABLE IV: maximum SBC values for different materials and defect sizes from PT and LIT

Material	Z (mm)	PT	LIT	
			Amp	Phase
Cu	0.3	2.53	3.44	3.18
	0.5	2.03	3.55	2.54
Al	0.3	10.41	5.54	7.63
	0.5	5.14	2.26	5.30
Polymer	0.3	49.79	10.18	31.20
	0.5	32.87	5.69	22.33

tently yields higher SBC values at both defect depths—3.44 for the 0.3 mm defect and 3.55 for the 0.5 mm defect—compared to PT, which records 2.53 and 2.03, respectively. This indicates a clear advantage of LIT for such materials. In contrast, for low diffusivity polymer, PT outperforms LIT at all defect depths, achieving maximum SBC values of 49.79 for the 0.3 mm defect and 32.87 for the 0.5 mm defect. Al, with thermal diffusivity between that of Cu and polymer, the shallower defect (0.3 mm) yields a maximum SBC of 10.41 with PT, while LIT achieves 5.54 for amplitude and 7.63 for phase. However, for the deeper defect (0.5 mm), LIT records 5.30 for phase, while PT records 5.14. This suggests that PT is more effective for shallower defects in Al, while LIT performs better for deeper defects.

V. CONCLUSION

This work presents a reduced complexity study on individual materials (Cu, Al, and polymers) chosen to span

a range of thermal diffusivities and containing artificially induced subsurface defects. The detection performance of PT and LIT is evaluated by comparing the resulting SBC values. As expected, across all materials, shallower defects yielded higher SBC values. In the case of low diffusivity polymer, PT produced higher SBC values than LIT, making it the preferred technique for subsurface defect detection in molded packages or for evaluating underfills. Conversely, for high diffusivity Cu, LIT shows better performance. For Al, with thermal diffusivity between that of Cu and polymer, PT is more effective for shallower defects, while LIT performs better for deeper defects. Therefore, assessments of Cu or Ag sintered die attach layers are best targeted with LIT, where appropriate selection of excitation frequency allows control of the thermal diffusion length to effectively detect voids and delamination.

Future work will primarily focus on LIT, as high thermal diffusivity materials are used in electronic packaging. The findings of this study will be applied to real structures, namely the die, die attach, substrate, and to enable reliable assessment of the die attach layer. Excitation frequencies will be fine-tuned to match the thermal diffusivity of the materials used in electronic packaging. In parallel, system limits will be quantified to define the detectability envelope and support reliable defect detection.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This project is supported by the MIRELAI project, which is funded by MSCA Horizon Doctoral Network from the European Union (Grant Agreement No. 101072491) and SmartMan project from the Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Action (Grant No. 13IK033E).

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